

STUDY OF THE *TREMOLO* TECHNIQUE ON THE ACOUSTIC GUITAR: EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND PRELIMINARY RESULTS ON REGULARITY

Sérgio Freire

School of Music

Federal University of Minas Gerais (UFMG)

sfreire@musica.ufmg.br

Lucas Nézio

School of Music (UFMG)

lucasnezio@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This paper presents an experimental setup for the study of right hand techniques on the acoustic guitar, and describes the main features of our apparatus regarding the extraction of audio descriptors. A preliminary case study on the *tremolo* technique is also discussed, where four different musicians played five versions of the same musical excerpt. These versions are compared on the basis of the regularity of the rhythmic pattern, the note durations, and the uniformity of the amplitudes. The comparison results suggest a direct relationship between rhythmic regularity and the player's level of expertise. Nevertheless, this relationship does not apply to the note durations or the dynamic regularity. Finally, some concerns regarding the difficulties in listening to the discovered (ir)regularities are addressed, and some steps for further research are pointed out.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of increasingly refined tools for audio processing, video analysis and motion capture has opened new methods for studying music performance. Several of these tools and methodologies can be seen in the multimodal (exploring more than one stream of data related to the same performance) projects developed at the Input Devices and Music Interaction Laboratory [1], McGill University, Canada.

On the other hand, the extraction of features and descriptors from only audio signals still receives much efforts and generates significant results [1–3].

The analysis of audio recordings of polyphonic or ensemble performances pose additional difficulties, especially in source and voice separation [4, 5]. Studies in this field are usually accomplished through independent recording of each musician or, as in the case of the piano, by using instruments such as the Disklavier, which can generate MIDI (or similar) data [6–8].

Fewer studies have focused on polyphonic performances on an acoustic guitar. Thus far, most of the existing liter-

ature deals with electric or commercial MIDI guitars, and some of them are not directly concerned with detailed features of the performance [9–12]. This paper presents the experimental setup and tools developed for studying the right hand techniques of an acoustic guitar player, along with the results and discussion of an experiment focused on the *tremolo* technique.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE SYSTEM

The setup used for this study consisted of the following components: a Spanish acoustic guitar Alhambra (model E-533, year 1978), hexaphonic acoustic pickups made by LR Baggs, a multi-cable with six independent audio paths, an audio interface with preamplification Focusrite Saffire Pro40, and the Max programming environment. Developing the system with real-time capabilities provides the potential not only to use it as a didactic tool, but also for interactive applications of the acoustic-digital interface. In non real-time applications, the software Digital Performer is used for the multi-track recording; these recordings may be later fed into Max through an internal audio driver.

The basic data related to signal levels in the system are presented in Table 1. The RMS values are expressed in dBFS (dB full scale), where 0 dB corresponds to the maximum undistorted signal admitted by the system. The calculation is done for each of the 1024 samples (corresponding to 21.3 ms at a sampling frequency of 48 kHz), with a hop size of 512 samples. These data were averaged from several informal performance sessions on this instrument. They also showed that the pickup system was sufficiently reliable and uniform to allow for comparison of the signal levels from different strings. The amplitude range, with an average of 39 dB, is consistent with the data collected by Gieseler [13] for an acoustic guitar (ca. 35 dB).

The mechanical and acoustic coupling is very strong in the guitar used in this setup, and deserves special attention in the routines of attack detection. Two general values were calculated for each string (see Table 2), using the same strategy of averaging informal performance sessions. The first value is the maximum influence suffered by one string due to a simultaneous attack on the remaining five strings. The second is the maximum influence of the attack on one string on the combined levels of the five remaining strings. The presence of sympathetic resonance may elevate these values somewhat.

string	tuning (Hz)	background noise(dB)	intensity attacks pp (dB)	intensity attacks ff (dB)
first (E4)	330	-89.6	-60	-23
second (B3)	247	-89	-62	-23
third (G3)	196	-88.7	-62	-20
fourth (D3)	147	-88.8	-60	-23
fifth (A2)	110	-89.4	-60	-23
sixth (E2)	82.5	-90	-60	-20

Table 1. Basic amplitude values in the system.

string	maximum influence from remaining strings (dB)	maximum influence on remaining strings (dB)
first	-48	-34
second	-45	-35
third	-44	-42
fourth	-45	-45
fifth	-45	-49
sixth	-45	-46

Table 2. General amplitude levels due to mechanical coupling in the system.

The audio signal generated by the pickups was compared to the sound captured by a condenser microphone of median sensibility [14]. Two main results are worth mentioning here. First, a consistent positive correlation was found in the different dynamic levels between signals from the two sources. Second, the differences in sonority were more noticeable, mainly in the bass and medium registers. The typical resonances of an acoustic guitar, due to the soundboard and sound hole, are missing in the pickup signals, as expected. However, the attack transients are more defined in these signals, and help the extraction of descriptors (see next section).

Currently, the system can produce several low-level audio descriptors in real-time: moment of attack detection and note offset (with an error margin of 10 ms), amplitude, pitch, articulation (staccato - legato), and pitch bending. Efforts are being made to characterize the brightness (taking in account the string and fret in use) and sympathetic resonance (both in amplitude and pitch effects).

Simple visual interfaces for the real-time monitoring of amplitudes, beat/pulse duration, and the effective duration of each note (a kind of piano-roll display) were developed. Preliminary studies have focused on right hand techniques like arpeggios, plaqué (block chords), repeated notes, and *tremolos*. Such studies were important not only for the development of analytical methods and tools, but also for the

calibration and progressive refinement of the system. They are discussed in detail in Nezio's dissertation [14]. Somewhat unexpected results from the analysis of two performances of a *tremolo* excerpt encouraged the realization of the present work, which has a larger number of interpreters and will be discussed later.

3. EXTRACTION OF NOTE ONSETS, OFFSETS AND AMPLITUDES

The majority of the sounds produced on the guitar may be characterized by a sharp attack followed by a resonance, with no sustained section. Therefore, it is not necessary for the purposes of this paper to distinguish between the onset and attack portions of the audio signal: on the guitar, an attack always presents a clear transient and a definite peak in the signal.

The extraction of note attacks, offsets and amplitudes is a crucial task in this system, and led to the development of a dedicated algorithm. The basic idea is to compare the peak amplitude value of the signal generated by one string with its RMS amplitude value (normally calculated on every 1024 samples). This RMS value may be re-placed by a variable floor value, depending on the signal levels present on the remaining strings. Figure 1 shows a general view of the processes and stages involved in this work, each of which will be discussed in detail below.

The first step is the filtering of the signal of the focused string, a stage called pre-processing by Bello [15]. Two band-pass filters are applied in parallel, the first in the low-medium register and the other in the high register. This contributes simultaneously to the diminution of the sympathetic resonances and to the amplification of transients. From this filtered signal, the peak value is extracted every 5 ms, and the average of the last two (sometimes three) values is calculated. This averaging avoids short bursts due to finger displacement or percussion to be interpreted as an attack.

The averaged peak value is then compared with the RMS signal of the same string or with a variable floor value, the chosen being the higher one. The floor value remains -60 dB (the low threshold of pp attacks, see Table 1) as far as the peak value of the combined signal of the remaining strings, calculated every 10 ms, does not exceed -50 dB. When this value surpasses -50 dB, a non-linear function, heuristically defined, generates a new floor value continuously.

For the comparison between the peak and the RMS (or floor) values, a two-step threshold detector is used (a digital version of a Schmitt trigger). The high threshold is determined by the RMS (or floor) value multiplied by a user parameter. In the process of fine tuning the algorithm, it was found that linking the low threshold to the high one was helpful; thus, the low value is calculated from the high value through a "release depth" factor, varying between 1.001 and 2.0. The higher this factor, the lower the incoming value must be to retrigger the detection. A minimum waiting time for the recognition of a new attack (re-attack) may also be set by the user.

Figure 1. Flowchart of the algorithm developed to extract note attacks and offsets and to estimate the amplitude.

Once an attack is detected, the process of amplitude calculation is started. Because of the unavoidable delay in the RMS calculation and psychoacoustic reasons (integration of sound intensity in the ear), the amplitude is defined as the maximum RMS value of the non-filtered signal that occurs between 0 and 80 ms after the attack detection. We believe that this value represents the dynamics intentions of the performer quite well, based on the comparisons between the signals generated by the pickups and a microphone, mentioned earlier in this paper.

The detection of the offset of notes is accomplished in one of the following ways: either the RMS value of the focused string has dropped below a predefined value, or a new attack has occurred before this happens.

The routine just described is applied to all strings simultaneously. With these three audio descriptors, it is possible to do a detailed analysis of the rhythmic and dynamic patterns of performances on an acoustic guitar.

4. ANALYSIS AND COMPARISON OF THE REGULARITY IN FIVE INTERPRETATIONS OF A TREMOLO EXCERPT

On the guitar, the *tremolo* technique consists of playing fast and repeatedly the same note on one string, searching for a more sustained sonority, which does not make part of the regular sound palette of the instrument. When using the finger-picking, this effect is achieved through the rapid alternation of the right hand fingers, indicated by the letters *p* (thumb, from the Spanish *pulgar*), *i* (index), *m* (middle) and *a* (ring or annular). A very common texture in the guitar literature is the use of the *tremolo* with the fingering *p a m i*, where the three last fingers make the *tremolo* using a treble string and the thumb plays a melody in a lower reg-

ister. This is what happens in the musical excerpt chosen for this study was the opening bars of the Scherzino - the third movement of Alexandre Tansman's Cavatina (1951), as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Initial bars of the Scherzino from Tansman's Cavatina, for guitar.

The musicians were asked to play it as normally expected in a music context, without any special instructions regarding tempo or dynamics. The guitarists were two undergraduate students (versions A e B), one graduate student (version C) and one professional guitarist (version D). One musician (A) played the excerpt twice, with an interval of about eight months, which is indicated by A1 and A2. The data generated by the real-time algorithm in Max were subsequently edited manually to bring the margin of error to a quasi sample-level precision. For the discussion that follows, is useful to name the set of four successive notes (*p a m i*) as a cycle; therefore, the excerpt has 4 bars, 24 cycles and 96 notes.¹

4.1 BPM Calculation

The general tempo of the excerpt may be calculated from inter-onset intervals (IOI) between the eighth notes played by the thumb (lower voice in Figure 2). All versions exhibit the pattern 4-2-2-3-2-4-2-3-2-4-3-2 (repeated twice) for the choice of the strings played by the thumb in every cycle. The *tremolo* proper is always played on the first string, with the left hand finger kept in a fixed position on the fretboard.

Figure 3 shows the BPM (beats per minute) curve for each version. Note that the first value in the graphic is calculated when the second note is attacked, and this applies to all subsequent values. There is no general beat pattern among these versions, although the alternation of pulse acceleration and deceleration (in a triangular shape) may be detected to some extent in some of them. The peak (on the onset of the fifth cycle) and the valley (onset of the sixth cycle) present in the otherwise quite regular execution C are due to the anticipation of the attack on the fourth string in the fifth cycle. This is followed immediately by a much delayed attack of the annular, which contributes to a lower BPM value in the sixth cycle. These irregularities can be seen in Figure 4 version D, which plots all notes against IOIs, as an inverted curve (valley and peak). The slowest version B shows the most regular pulse, and the irregularity of the remaining versions may be attributed to the difficulties of playing *tremolos* in a faster tempo. Nevertheless,

¹ Recordings of these versions can be downloaded at: <https://dl.dropbox.com/u/25793338/versionsAtoD.zip>

version D shows a high level of technical control and regularity in each cycle, as will be seen in the next subsection.

Figure 3. BPM curves for each version.

4.2 IOI Calculation

Figures 4 depict the IOIs between every attack in all versions. In some of them, clear regular patterns can be seen, especially in versions B and D. These graphics may lead to the supposition that these musicians have a highly internalized, quasi-mechanized way of executing this technique, which, owing to its speed, does not allow a conscious control of every attack. In the versions B and D, the peaks are always connected to a thumb attack, meaning that some extra time is interposed between each cycle. Version C also sometimes follows this pattern, but it is not systematic as the former ones. Another very distinct characteristic of version D is that the valleys in the curve always correspond to attacks made by the median finger (third note in the cycle). This feature points to a performance strategy based on an irregular regularity: the cycle is not played with constant interval times, although a clear time pattern can be observed. In each cycle, there is an acceleration from the thumb to the median finger attack (passing by the annular), then a deceleration from the middle to the thumb (passing by the index).

4.3 Normalized Durations on the First String

Relevant information about performance strategies may also be drawn from the effective duration (interval between the note attack and offset) of each note played on the first string. This may be related not only to the bio-mechanical aspect of this technique, but also to the desired sonority. The longer the duration the more sustained is the whole effect of the *tremolo*. Figure 5 shows a normalized value for the durations on the y-axis, which means that the duration of the note attacked by the index finger (the fourth in the cycle) is halved.

Versions A1 and D both exhibit longer durations in the last note of the cycle, which is expected, since the next attack is made on another string. Nevertheless, the shorter durations show different behaviours: while A1, on the average, produces two different durations for the notes played by the annular and median fingers in each cycle, musician C maintains almost systematically equally very short durations for these notes. The waveforms representing typical cycles from these versions can be seen in Figures 6(a) and 6(b).

Figure 4. IOIs in ms from (a) version A1, (b) version A2, (c) version B, (d) version C, (e) version D.

4.4 Amplitudes in Each Layer of the Excerpt

As in the former analysis of note durations, the amplitudes series can also help the analysis of the performance in both technical and interpretative terms. On the technical side, the main feature is again the uniformity observed in the first string. On the musical side, two different ways of interpreting the lower voice of the excerpt showed up: one considers the voice as one single stream, the other splits the notes in two melodies, one acting as a bass line (on the fourth string) and the other as a tenor line (on strings 3 and 2).

Figure 7 shows the amplitudes on the first string in versions A2 and D. It can be noted that version A2 is more uniform in this respect: its values are distributed across a narrower dynamic range and neighbor notes have more similar amplitude values. On the other hand, version D, the most regular on timing patterns, shows a very irregular amplitude series.

Figure 8 plots the amplitudes of the lower layer of the versions A1, B, and D. Version B clearly divides this layer in two voices, the bass line being the softer. Version A1

Figure 5. (a) Normalized note durations on the first string from version A1. (b) Normalized note durations on the first string from version D.

Figure 6. (a) Waveform of the notes played on the first string in cycles 9 and 10 in version A1. (b) Waveform of the notes played on the first string in cycles 4 and 5 in version D.

makes no such subdivision, and version D is somewhere in between the former two.

4.5 Spectral Features

We have not yet developed a method to study the regularity of timbre in the *tremolo* technique, although the sharpness of the attacks has certainly a strong influence on the spectrum of such short sounds. The balance between the attacks played by three different fingers (index, medium and annular) is surely another technical challenge for guitarists playing *tremolos*. The sonograms of the recordings shown in Figures 6(a) and 6(b) illustrate some aspects of this issue, as can be seen in Figures 9(a) and 9(b). It is worth noting the very dissimilar spectra of each note in the cycles of version D, and the salient offset transients in version A1.

5. FINAL REMARKS

The above discussion has indicated some relevant characteristics of the *tremolo* technique on an acoustic guitar.

Figure 7. Amplitude curves on the first string in versions A2 and D.

Figure 8. Amplitude curves on the lower layer (fourth, third and second strings) in versions A1, B and D.

Figure 9. (a) Sonogram of cycles 4 and 5 from version A1. (b) Sonogram of cycles 9 and 10 from version D.

None of the versions scored equally high in the different parameters related to regularity and uniformity. Nevertheless, the more trained musicians demonstrated a very fine control and regularity of movements. The less skilled performers in this technique have somehow brought into play relevant interpretative features, like longer durations and more regular amplitudes.

It is very difficult to perceive some of the characteristics described above during the performances. It is also hard to accept some of these results, which disagree strongly with a naïve, but theoretically justified, assumption of very regular IOIs in this excerpt. Listening to a single rhythmic structure - constructed with filtered audio clicks featuring the timing and amplitudes from the discussed versions - provides a better way for the perceiving such irregularities.

When both recordings – the performance on guitar and the rhythmic audio reduction – are superimposed, the missing factors in the analysis come into play. First, a stream segregation process is certainly taking place, dividing the excerpt in two (or three) streams, and preventing a unified perception of the global rhythm. The tiny differences in each note of the *tremolo* – type of attack, amplitude, duration – may also contribute to a more diffuse perception

of the rhythm. Finally, the fact that the lower voice keeps sounding above the rapid *tremolos* also helps integrating the silences present in between these notes.

Future works may tackle the *tremolo* technique in a multimodal environment, using video images with high frame rates and 3D motion capture, where the correlations between the mechanical execution of the gestures and the effective production of sound may be traced.

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